

ON THE TENSILE RESPONSE OF A FIBER REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

C.H. Weber, S.J. Connell and F.W. Zok

Materials Department
University of California
Santa Barbara, California 93106

1. INTRODUCTION

The addition of continuous ceramic fibers to metal alloys can impart substantial improvements in creep resistance. Some of the basic features of the axial creep response of unidirectionally-reinforced materials can be understood by considering an ideal case in which the fibers are elastic (non-creeping) and have a deterministic tensile strength, S . Such features are illustrated in Figure 1. Under conditions of *constant applied stress*, σ , two types of behavior can be obtained, depending on the magnitude of σ (Figure 1(a)). (i) When σ is less than the fiber bundle strength, fS (with f being the fiber volume fraction), the axial creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$, decreases continuously with the axial strain, ϵ , and asymptotically approaches zero at a strain, $\epsilon = \sigma/E_f$, where E_f is the elastic modulus of the fibers. In this limit, all of the load supported by the matrix has been shed to the fibers. (ii) When the stress exceeds the fiber bundle strength ($\sigma > fS$), the creep rate begins to decrease with ϵ , but, at a critical strain, $\epsilon^* = S/E_f$, the fibers and the composite fracture catastrophically. Under conditions of *constant applied strain rate*, the creep response can be characterized by the variation in the tangent modulus, $d\sigma/d\epsilon$, with strain. In this case, the tangent modulus decreases monotonically with strain, reaching a limiting value of fE_f when the matrix stress falls to zero. For all strain rates, fracture occurs at the critical strain, $\epsilon^* = S/E_f$ (as it does under constant stress conditions).

In reality, ceramic fibers exhibit a statistical distribution of strengths, and consequently, the fibers within a composite fracture over a *range* of strains. This distribution is expected to lead to an increase in the limiting strain under constant stress conditions (above σ/E_f), and a reduction in the limiting tangent modulus under constant strain rate conditions (below fE_f). Furthermore, the magnitude of such effects is expected to be influenced by the shear resistance, τ , of the fiber-matrix interface, as this resistance governs the process of load transfer from the matrix to the ends of the broken fibers. The present article describes an experimental investigation of the effects of both the fiber strength distribution and the interface sliding resistance on the tensile response of a unidirectional composite, along with comparisons with predictions of existing models.

2. EXPERIMENTS

The material used in this study was a Ti-6Al-4V alloy reinforced with 32% unidirectional SiC (σ) fibers (produced by British Petroleum). Straight tensile specimens, with dimensions 150 mm long x 6 mm wide, were cut parallel to the fiber axis. Aluminum tabs were then bonded to the specimen ends. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature at a strain rate of $8.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and at 600°C at a strain rate of $1.7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The axial strains were measured using a contacting extensometer.

Figure 1 Schematic diagrams showing the expected creep response of unidirectional MMCs containing elastic fibers: (a) constant applied stress, σ ; (b) constant applied strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$.

The in-situ fiber strength characteristics were determined by conducting tensile tests on ~ 50 fibers, extracted from the pristine composite by dissolving the matrix in a 30% HF solution. The fibers were attached to cardboard tabs, and tested at a strain rate of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The fiber gauge length was fixed at 25 mm. The results of these tests were compared with those corresponding to as-processed fibers (prior to composite consolidation).

The interface sliding resistance was measured using single fiber push-out tests. Specimens were prepared by cutting thin sections ($\sim 700\text{-}1000 \mu\text{m}$) transverse to the fibers and subsequently polishing both sides to remove machining damage. The final specimen thickness was typically in the range of $400\text{-}700 \mu\text{m}$. The matrix on one side of each specimen was then etched to a depth of $\sim 30\text{-}50 \mu\text{m}$, leaving the fibers protruding above the matrix surface. The specimens were placed onto a flat support base, with the selected fiber positioned above a small ($500 \mu\text{m}$) diameter hole. Embedded within the support base was a series of pyrolytic graphite heating elements, capable of heating the base to $\sim 800^\circ\text{C}$. The fibers were pushed out the matrix using a cylindrical indenter made from the SiC fibers themselves. The measured load-displacement characteristics were used to determine the interface sliding resistance at the onset of sliding [1]. Tests were conducted at both room temperatures and 600°C .

3. RESULTS

3.1 Composite

The results of the uniaxial tensile tests, showing the effects of test temperature, are presented in Figure 2. At room temperature, the composite is initially linear elastic, with a modulus, $E \approx 195 \pm 7 \text{ GPa}$. This value is consistent with one calculated from the rule of mixtures ($E = 206 \text{ GPa}$), taking the matrix modulus to be $E_m = 115 \text{ GPa}$ and the fiber modulus $E_f = 400 \text{ GPa}$. At a strain of $\sim 0.75\%$, the tangent modulus drops precipitously (by $\sim 30\%$), a result of matrix yielding. Beyond this point, the tangent modulus remains at a level of $\sim fE_f$, until fracture occurs at a strain of $\sim 1.0\%$. At 600°C , the initial tangent modulus (at $\epsilon \sim 0$), is close to fE_f , suggesting that the matrix supports a negligible fraction of the stress at this strain rate. Upon further loading, the tangent modulus decreases, reaching a value of $\sim 0.75 fE_f$ at the failure strain (0.8%). This reduction in tangent modulus (below fE_f) suggests that substantial fiber fracture occurs prior to composite fracture.

3.2 Fibers

The results of the fiber tensile tests are presented in Figure 3. Evidently the fibers undergo a substantial reduction in mean strength following composite fabrication along with an increase in the breadth of the strength distribution. The results for both the pristine fibers and the fibers extracted from the composite can be well represented by the two parameter Weibull distribution:

$$P_s = \exp - \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \tag{1}$$

where P_s is the cumulative survival probability in a gauge length, L , σ_0 and L_0 are the reference values of stress and length (the latter taken to be 1m.) and m is the shape parameter (or Weibull modulus). Results of the regression analysis (following Equation 1) are indicated on Figure 3.

Figure 2 Results of the tensile tests showing effects of temperature on (a) the stress-strain response, and (b) the variation in tangent modulus with strain.

Figure 3 Comparison of fiber strength distributions before and after composite consolidation. The results for the fibers "off-spool" have been taken from an extensive body of data, comprised of > 1000 fiber tests conducted by the fiber manufacturer (British Petroleum).

3.3 Interfaces

The fiber push-out tests indicate that, at room temperature, the interface sliding resistance is $\tau \approx 120$ MPa. At 600°C , the sliding stress is reduced substantially, to $\tau \approx 45$ MPa. The reduction in τ is presumably a result of the relaxation of thermal residual stresses with increasing temperature.

4. MODELING

In general, the flow or creep response of a unidirectional metal matrix composite can be written as

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = (1-f) \sigma_m(\epsilon) + f \sigma_f(\epsilon) \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma(\epsilon)$ is the composite stress at a strain, ϵ , and $\sigma_m(\epsilon)$ and $\sigma_f(\epsilon)$ are the current volume-averaged stresses in the matrix and the fiber, respectively. Consequently, the tangent modulus of the composite is

$$\frac{d\sigma(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = (1-f) \frac{d\sigma_m(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} + f \frac{d\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

To proceed further, expressions for $\sigma_m(\epsilon)$ and $\sigma_f(\epsilon)$ are required. Two limiting cases for the matrix can be readily obtained. (i) If the matrix is elastic, perfectly-plastic, with a yield strain, ϵ_y , the matrix contribution to the stress and tangent modulus are

$$\sigma_m(\epsilon) = E \epsilon \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{d\sigma_m(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = E \quad (5)$$

in the regime $0 \leq \epsilon \leq \epsilon_y$, and

$$\sigma_m(\epsilon) = E \epsilon_y \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{d\sigma_m(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = 0 \quad (7)$$

in the regime $\epsilon > \epsilon_y$. (ii) If the temperature is sufficiently high or the strain rate sufficiently low, the matrix contribution to the composite response becomes negligible, whereupon

$$\sigma_m(\epsilon) \rightarrow 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{d\sigma_m(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} \rightarrow 0 \quad (9)$$

Similarly, limits can be placed on the fiber stress, depending on the assumed fiber strength distribution and the interface shear resistance. (i) If the fiber strength is deterministic (given by S), the fiber stress and tangent modulus are simply

$$\sigma_f(\epsilon) = E_f \epsilon \quad (10)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{d\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = E_f \quad (11)$$

for $\epsilon < S/E_f$. These results are *independent* of the interface shear resistance and provide upper bounds to the cases considered below. (ii) If the fiber strength is statistical, the solution for $\sigma_f(\epsilon)$

becomes more complex. The solution is obtained in two steps. In the first, the progressive fragmentation of the fibers with applied strain is computed in terms of the parameters that characterize the fiber strength distribution (σ_o and m). This requires consideration of the process of load transfer from the matrix to the ends of the broken fibers via the interfacial shear tractions. The load transfer leads to a progressive build-up of tensile stress within the broken fibers, with the potential of multiple failure sites along an individual fiber. The second step involves calculating the average axial stress supported by the fibers in terms of the fragment lengths and the stress distribution along the fibers.

The problem of fiber fragmentation has been analyzed rigorously by Curtin [2,3], subject to three assumptions: (a) the fiber strength is described by a Weibull distribution (Equation 1), (b) the fibers are coupled to the matrix through a *constant* interface shear resistance, τ , and (c) the load associated with broken fibers is shed uniformly through the composite in the plane of the break, corresponding to so-called "global load sharing" conditions [4]. The key result from Curtin's analysis applicable to the present study is the approximate analytical expression

$$\frac{\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{E_f} = \epsilon \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\epsilon E_f}{\sigma_o} \right)^{m+1} \left(\frac{\sigma_o}{\tau} \right) \left(\frac{R}{L_o} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

which, upon differentiation, becomes,

$$\frac{1}{E_f} \frac{d\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = 1 - \left(\frac{m+2}{2} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon E_f}{\sigma_o} \right)^{m+1} \left(\frac{\sigma_o}{\tau} \right) \left(\frac{R}{L_o} \right). \quad (13)$$

These results are valid only if the specimen gauge length exceeds a characteristic fiber fragment length, δ_c , defined by [2,3]

$$\delta_c = \left(\frac{\sigma_o R L_o^{1/m}}{\tau} \right)^{m/(m+1)} \quad (14)$$

In the present Ti/SiC composite, $\delta_c \approx 5$ mm at room temperature and $\delta_c \approx 11$ mm at 600°C: both values being substantially lower than the specimen gauge length. (iii) If the fiber strength follows a Weibull distribution, but the specimen gauge length is less than δ_c , a lower bound on the average fiber stress is obtained by taking the stress in the broken fibers to be zero. This approach is equivalent to the one used in analyzing failure of a dry fiber bundle. The relevant results in this regime are

$$\frac{\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{E_f} = \epsilon \exp \left[\frac{-L}{L_o} \left(\frac{\epsilon E_f}{\sigma_o} \right)^m \right] \quad (15)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{1}{E_f} \frac{d\sigma_f(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} = \left[1 - m \frac{L}{L_o} \left(\frac{\epsilon E_f}{\sigma_o} \right)^m \right] \exp \left[\frac{-L}{L_o} \left(\frac{\epsilon E_f}{\sigma_o} \right)^m \right]. \quad (16)$$

5. COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORY AND EXPERIMENT

The predictions of the foregoing models have been compared with the experimental results on the Ti/SiC composite. The room temperature results have been modeled assuming the matrix to be elastic, perfectly-plastic, whereupon Equations (5) and (7) apply. In contrast, the high temperature results have been modeled assuming the matrix stress to be zero (an assumption supported by the

measurements of $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$ at small strains). In both cases, the Weibull parameters derived from the single fiber tensile tests ($\sigma_0 = 3.9$ GPa and $m = 5$), and the measured interface shear resistances ($\tau = 120$ MPa at room temperature and $\tau = 45$ MPa at 600°C) have been combined with Equations (13) and (16) to obtain the relevant limits on $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$. These results have been combined with Equation 3, leading to the trends plotted on Figure 4.

The prediction of $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$ from Curtin's model is broadly consistent with the results of tests conducted at room temperature. However, the predicted failure strain (corresponding to the point where $d\sigma/d\varepsilon = 0$) is somewhat higher than the measured value (1.0% vs. 1.24%). Furthermore, the predicted tangent modulus at strains beyond the yield strain are slightly lower than the measurements. This discrepancy may be attributable to work hardening of the Ti matrix following yield (assumed to be zero in the model). In addition, it should be noted that the model based on dry fiber bundle behavior (Equation 16) strongly underestimates both the tangent modulus and the failure strain, consistent with the implicit assumption that no coupling exists between the fibers and the matrix. In contrast, the correlation between experiment and theory at 600°C is poorer. Indeed, the measured reduction in $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$ at very small strains ($\sim 0.1\%$) falls below even the *lower bound* estimate of $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$ based on the room temperature strength of the extracted fibers. This result suggests that the strength of the fibers is reduced at elevated temperatures, perhaps resulting from interactions with the matrix alloy or the fiber coating. Here, again, the predicted failure strain from Curtin's model exceeds the measured value (0.8% vs. 1.1%).

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present results indicate that the room temperature tensile response of the Ti-SiC can be adequately described through a simple one-dimensional model, accounting for both the distribution of fiber strength and the process of load transfer from the matrix to the broken fiber ends, as detailed by Curtin. However, the predictions of failure strain appear to consistently overestimate the measurements. This trend may be attributable to local elevations in stress around broken fibers, leading to premature failure.

The discrepancies between the theory and the experiments at elevated temperature indicate two additional outstanding issues. The first relates to the in-situ strength of the fibers at elevated temperature, particularly after extended periods at temperature. The reactions that occur between the fiber, the coating and the matrix, and the impact of such reactions on fiber strength are not

Figure 4 Comparison of the model prediction with experimental measurements at (a) room temperature and (b) 600°C .

presently understood. Second, the relevant sliding stress at elevated temperature at low strain rates may be considerably lower than the value measured (at rather high rates) in the push-out test. It is expected that the shear stresses near the fiber-matrix interface during creep loading may be relaxed by flow within the matrix itself. This suggestion is consistent with the poor creep resistance of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy at 600°C. These issues are currently under investigation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency through the University Research Initiative under ONR contract N-00014-93-1-0224. The authors would like to thank Dr. John Porter of Rockwell International for assistance with the fiber testing.

REFERENCES

1. P.D. Warren, T.J. Mackin and A.G. Evans, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, **40** (1992), 1243-49.
2. W.A. Curtin, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, **74** (1991), 2837-45.
3. W.A. Curtin, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **26** (1991).
4. M.Y. He, A.G. Evans and W.A. Curtin, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, in press (1993).